

Composition of Prussian and Turnbull's Blue. Part II. Study of the Constituents of their Filtrates.

BY ABANI K. BHATTACHARYA.

In a previous communication (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240) it has been shown that Prussian and Turnbull's blue differ in their composition when freshly prepared by mixing the reacting constituents in equivalent proportions; but on ageing, the two compounds tend to be identical in composition and to assume a formula which is the mean of Prussian and Turnbull's blue, $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$ and $\text{Fe}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$ respectively; or in other words, both the blues tend to approach the simplest formula $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CN})_5$ wherein $\text{Fe} : \text{CN} = 1 : 2.5$.

It had also been urged that during the precipitation of Prussian blue, formation of some ferrous and ferricyanogen ion takes place as a result of mutual oxidation and reduction. Similarly during the precipitation of Turnbull's blue there would be some ferric and ferrocyanogen ions produced. In consequence of this, both Prussian and Turnbull's blue would tend towards a composition intermediate between ferrous ferricyanide and ferric ferricyanide.

The analysis of the filtrates of Prussian and Turnbull's blue was carried out to find whether mutual oxidation and reduction actually took place and the results are recorded in this paper.

The filtrates of the blues were prepared by mixing the solutions of the reacting substances in equivalent proportions. The mixture was made up to a litre in each case and the supernatant liquid was tested for the products of mutual oxidation and reduction as well as for the residual reactants.

. When ferric chloride and potassium ferricyanide are mixed in equivalent proportions, no residual reactants could be detected with filtrate but when potassium ferrocyanide is added in excess, ferricyanide appears in the filtrate as shown by the liberation of iodine from potassium iodide. The filtrate does not give any test for ferrous sulphate, no matter in what proportions the reactants are added.

When ferrous sulphate and potassium ferricyanide are mixed in equivalent proportion, an appreciable amount of ferrous sulphate and a trace of ferric salt appear in the filtrate. If potassium ferricyanide is added in excess, the filtrate decolourises very dilute solution of potassium permanganate showing the formation of ferrocyanide. This has also been confirmed by mixing small quantities of ferric chloride to the solution of ferrous sulphate before addition of an equivalent quantity of ferricyanide.

TABLE I.

$M/2.5\text{-FeSO}_4$ mixed with varying quantities of $M/2.5\text{-FeCl}_3$ was added to the required volume of $M/2.5\text{-K}_3\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ so as to give total precipitate of 0.125 g. Total volume kept constant at 50 c.c.

$M/2.5\text{-FeCl}_3$ added (c.c.)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
Action of NH_4CNS	Nil	Nil	Nil	Red	Deep red

It follows from the above experiments that with the removal of ferric chloride, there should be a corresponding excess of ferrous sulphate that remains unacted upon at the end of the reaction; and this is also shown by experiments recorded in Table II.

TABLE II.

Equivalent quantities of FeSO_4 and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ were mixed in presence of varying quantities of FeCl_3 as to give 0.25 g. of the precipitate. Total volume kept at 100 c.c. The ferrous salt, unacted upon, was titrated with KMnO_4 .

$M/2.5\text{-FeCl}_3$ added.	$N/26.84\text{-KMnO}_4$ required.	FeSO_4 unreacted.
0 c.c.	3.0 c.c.	0.1698 g.
0.2	3.5	0.1982
0.4	4.0	0.2266
0.6	5.0	0.2834
0.8	5.0	0.2834

The foregoing observations lend support to the view that some potassium ferrocyanide is undoubtedly formed in the above reaction;

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the ferrocyanide reacts with the little ferric chloride which had been added to ferrous sulphate before it was mixed with potassium ferri-cyanide.

It was further observed that the filtrate of Turnbull's blue de-colourised permanganate solution even after the ferrous sulphate had been removed as hydroxide by ammonia. Qualitative test for cyanide gave no indication of its presence. The reducing constituent was found to be an oxalate when tested for in the usual way after removal of the sulphate from the filtrate.

TABLE III

Analysis of reducing substances.

Equivalent quantities of FeSO_4 and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ were mixed in the following concentrations to produce 2.5 g. of the precipitate. Volume was kept constant at 1 litre. The values obtained on immediate titration with KMnO_4 correspond to ferrous salt and oxalate where ferrous salt was not removed and to only oxalate where ferrous salt had been removed as hydroxide. The values recorded after 24 hours correspond to total reducing substances in either cases. Estimations for 50 c.c. are given.

Conc. of mixing $\text{FeSO}_4 : \text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	Reducing substances in terms of FeSO_4 present		of $N/5.15\text{KMnO}_4$. FeSO_4 removed	
	Immediate reduction.	Total reduction.	Immediate reduction.	Total reduction.
M/5 : M/5	0.91 c.c.	2.36 c.c.	0.25 c.c.	0.77 c.c.
M/10 : M/10	0.91	2.36	0.25	0.77
M/25 : M/25	0.89	2.36	0.28	0.79

TABLE IV

Quantities of FeSO_4 and $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ calculated from the results given in Table III.

Conc. of mixing	FeSO_4	$\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$.	Undetected reducing agents in terms of $N/5.15\text{-KMnO}_4$.
M/5 : M/5	0.3894 g./litre	0.04370 g./litre	1.45 c.c.
M/10 : M/10	0.3894	0.04370	1.45
M/25 : M/25	0.3600	0.04892	1.47

Prussian blues prepared in the same proportions as given in the foregoing tables 'by mixing ferric chloride with potassium ferrocyanide' were kept in the dark and also exposed to sunlight, but neither oxalic acid nor ferric or ferrous salts could be detected in their filtrates.

DISCUSSION.

It seems that the appearance of potassium ferricyanide on adding excess of potassium ferrocyanide and its absence from the filtrate when ferric chloride and potassium ferrocyanide are mixed in equivalent proportions cannot be completely explained by a purely chemical explanation as given by Woringer (*Chem. Z.*, 1912, 36, 78). In all probability, the phenomenon of adsorption plays also an important part in removing the free potassium ferricyanide which is formed in accordance with the following reactions :

Adsorption of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ by Prussian blue and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ by Turnbull's blue has been studied and the results published (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240) will show that potassium ferrocyanide is appreciably adsorbed by Prussian blue, and the adsorption of potassium ferricyanide by Turnbull's blue, though much less than the corresponding values of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ adsorbed by Prussian blue, was not negligible. In view of the adsorption effects shown by Prussian blue, the author is of opinion that the little potassium ferricyanide that is formed by mutual oxidation and reduction is partly used up in forming ferrous ferricyanide or Turnbull's blue, and the residue is adsorbed by the precipitates, whereas, when potassium ferrocyanide is added in excess, the ferrocyanogen ions are sufficiently adsorbed by the precipitate and hence potassium ferricyanide is set free in the solution. It is also to be noted in the foregoing scheme of reactions

that for each molecule of potassium ferricyanide formed, only two-thirds of it is used up by ferrous chloride leaving a residual quantity of ferricyanide which, if not adsorbed by the precipitate, should appear in the solution and this condition is favoured by mixing potassium ferrocyanide in excess.

When ferrous sulphate is mixed with potassium ferricyanide, the following changes are likely to take place. :

According to the above scheme, the existence of residual ferrous sulphate in the filtrate can be explained as in equation (IV). The formation of oxalic acid may also be explained on the assumption that part of the hydrocyanic acid is oxidised to cyanogen $(\text{CN})_2$ which on hydrolysis forms oxalic acid. For the other reducing agents not yet identified, it seems probable that nitrogenous organic reducing substances are formed with the intervention of hydrocyanic acid.

When dried precipitates of Prussian and Turnbull's blues are boiled, a small fraction assumes a colloidal character. It is quite stable and coagulation can only be effected by adding an electrolyte.

Estimation of moisture in air-dried preparations of Prussian and Turnbull's blues was carried out by taking weighed quantities of them in a crucible and heating in the air oven at 100° till the weight was found constant. The following table gives the total amount of moisture retained by prussian and turnbull's blues.

TABLE V.

Conc. of mixing.	Moisture in Prussian blue.	Moisture in Turnbull's blue.
<i>M/5 : M/5</i>	16.72 %	18.16 %
<i>M/10 : M/10</i>	15.79	17.47
<i>M/25 : M/25</i>	16.16	19.30
Average	16.22	18.30

The samples of the blues dried in steam oven on exposure to the atmosphere regained the moisture lost in several days, the rate of increase in weight of turnbull's blue being a little slow.

Experiments on the study of colloidal Prussian and Turnbull's blues are in progress.

SUMMARY.

1. The formation of some quantity of potassium ferricyanide on adding ferric chloride to potassium ferrocyanide has been detected when potassium ferrocyanide is in excess.

2. On adding ferrous sulphate to potassium ferricyanide, some quantity of potassium ferrocyanide is formed. This has been indirectly shown by the removal of ferric chloride already added to the reacting ferrous sulphate from the field of reaction when the latter acts on potassium ferricyanide.

3. Presence of oxalic acid has also been detected in the filtrate and estimated.

4. Percentage of moisture retained by Prussian and Turnbull's blues has been estimated and the change produced on boiling the blues in water for a few hours has been observed.

In conclusion, I express my indebtedness to Prof. N. R. Dhar and Dr. S. Ghosh for their help and interest in the work.

Dark Reaction between Sodium Formate and iodine.

BY S. S. DOOSAJ AND W. V. BHAGWAT.

The reaction between sodium formate and iodine was studied by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) and the order of the reaction with respect to sodium formate and iodine was found to be unity. We have studied this reaction at different temperatures and have also determined the effect on sodium acetate, potassium chloride, potassium bromide and potassium iodide on this reaction. Our results are recorded below:.

Order of the Reaction.

This was determined by Ostwald's isolation method, by varying the concentration of sodium formate which was always kept high. Thus if k_1 and k_2 be the velocity coefficients when the concentrations of sodium formate are c_1 and c_2 , then the order n of the reaction with respect to sodium formate is given by

$$n = \frac{\log k_1/k_2}{\log c_1/c_2}.$$

TABLE I.

KI=44.664 g./litre. I₂=6.6934 g./litre. HCOONa=122 g./litre. 50 C.c. of each solution mixed together and 10 c.c. of mixture titrated each time.

Time.	Thiosulphate required.	$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log a/a-x.$
0 min.	11 c.c.	
17	6.2	0.0146
40.25	2.85	0.0145
54	1.8	0.0144
		<hr/>
		mean 0.0145

The velocity coefficients for other concentrations of sodium formate are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

$I_2 + KI$ (g./litre).	Na formate (g./litre).	$k = \frac{1}{t} \log a/a \cdot x.$	$n = \frac{\log k_1/k_2}{\log c_1/c_2}.$
6.6934 I_2 + 44.664 KI	(i) 122	(a) 0.0145	$\log \frac{a}{b} / \log \frac{i}{ii} = 1$
	(ii) 97.6	(b) 0.0116.	$\log \frac{c}{b} / \log \frac{iii}{ii} = 1$
	(iii) 36.6	(c) 0.00436	$\log \frac{d}{c} / \log \frac{iv}{iii} = 1$
	(iv) 12.2	(d) 0.00147	$\log \frac{e}{d} / \log \frac{v}{iv} = 1$
	(v) 6.1	(e) 0.000729

Hence the reaction is directly proportional to the concentration of iodine and also to the concentration of sodium formate and hence the total order of the reaction is 2.

Effect of Sodium Acetate.

Sodium formate is easily oxidised by iodine at the ordinary temperature and the course of the reaction is represented by the equation,

Dhar (*loc. cit.*) has used an excess of sodium acetate to regulate the reaction as the hydrogen ions, formed as a product of the change, greatly retard the reaction. We have studied the effect of sodium acetate on this reaction and observed that when concentration of sodium formate is sufficiently high, the reaction velocity is regular even without the addition of sodium acetate and the amount of sodium acetate has practically no effect on the velocity constant.

TABLE III.

KI = 44.664 g./litre. I₂ = 6.6934 g./litre. HCOONa = 122 g./litre.

50 C.c. of I₂ solution + 50 c.c. of HCOONa solution mixed and 10 c.c. of the mixture titrated each time at 30°.

Sodium acetate = nil			Sodium acetate = 6.884 g./100 c. c. mixture.		
Time.	Thio.	k ₁ .	Time.	Thio.	k ₁ .
0 min.	11 c.c.	—	0	13	—
17	6.2	0.0146	22	6.5	0.0136
40.25	2.85	0.0145	35	4.05	0.0144
54	1.8	0.0144	55	2.06	0.0146
		<u>mean 0.0145</u>			<u>mean 0.0145</u>

Other results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Na-acetate in g./100 c.c. mixture.	k ₁ at 16°.	k ₁ at 21°.	k ₁ at 26°.
0	0.001673	0.00364	0.00756
5	0.001670	0.00364	0.00753
10	0.001670	0.00364	0.00753
20	0.001674	0.00364	0.00753

It is thus clear that sodium acetate is not necessary to regulate the reaction when the concentration of sodium formate is high.

Effect of Potassium Iodide.

This reaction is retarded by the addition of potassium iodide due to the decrease in the amount of free iodine as KI₃ is formed according to the equation $KI + I_2 \rightleftharpoons KI_3$.

TABLE V.

KI=2.2331 g./100 c.c. mixture at 21°			KI=7.2231 g./100 c.c. of the mixture.	
Time.	Thio.	k_1 .	Thio.	k_1 .
0 min.	16.6 c.c.	—	16.75 c.c.	—
25	13.45	0.00365	15.7	0.00112
50	9.9	0.00365	14.7	0.00113
75	8.8	0.00361	13.7	0.00116
	mean	0.00364	mean	0.00114

Other results may be summarised as follows :

TABLE VI.

KI. g./100 c.c. of mixture.	k_1 at 21°.	k_1 at 26°.
2.2331	0.00364	0.007406
7.2331	0.00114	0.002654
12.2331	0.0008261	0.00160
22.2331	0.000320	...

TABLE VII.

Temp.	Ratio of k_1 .	Ratio of KI conc.	Ratio of KI conc./ratio of k_1 .
21°	3.28	3.21	1.00
	4.4	5.3	1.20
	11.4	10.1	0.90
26°	2.85	3.2	1.14
	4.62	5.3	1.14

The relation between the amount of KI and the velocity coefficient is represented in Table VII.

These results show that the velocity coefficient does not fall directly as the concentration of potassium iodide but by a power which is less than the direct.

Effect of Potassium Bromide.

It is observed that the velocity coefficient is unaffected by the addition of potassium bromide.

TABLE VIII.

Temp. = 21°		Temp. = 26°	
KBr (g./100 c.c. of mixture).	k_1 .	KBr (g./100 c.c. of mixture).	k_1 .
0	0.00408	0	0.00778
5	0.00408	5	0.00773
10	0.00404	10	0.00774
20	0.00409	20	0.00775

Effect of Potassium Chloride.

We have varied the concentration of potassium chloride and observed that the velocity of the reaction increases with the concentration of potassium chloride. Ghosh and Purkayastha (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **B.**, 7, 276, 285), has observed the same in case of the reactions between organo-hydroxy acids and bromine. Our results are given in Table IX.

TABLE IX.

Temp. 21°.

KCl = nil.			KCl = 8.987 g./100 c.c. mixture.		
Time.	Thio.	k_1 .	Time.	Thio.	k_1 .
0 min	15.3 c.c.	—	0	15.1 c.c.	—
25	12.4	0.00365	20	12.2	0.00481
40	10.9	0.00368	40	9.6	0.00491
60	9.25	0.00365	60	7.9	0.00470
		mean 0.00366			mean 0.00481

Other results are summarised in Table X.

TABLE X.

Temp.	KCl (g./100 c.c. of mixture).	Diff. in amount of KCl.	k_1 .	Diff. in k_1 .	$\frac{\text{Diff. of } k_1}{\text{Diff. of KCl}}$
26°	0	—	0.00740	—	—
	5	5	0.00813	0.00073	0.000146
	10	10	0.00892	0.00152	0.000152
	20	20	0.01010	0.00270	0.00135

The results in the last column show that the increase in velocity coefficient is proportional to the concentration of KCl.

Temperature Coefficient of the Dark Reaction.

We have varied the amount of sodium formate and the velocity coefficient at different temperatures so obtained are summarised below.

TABLE XI.

Na-formate (g./litre)	100	80	50	30
k_1 at 16°	0·00161	0·00130	0·000788	0·000549
k_1 at 21°	0·00363	0·00290	0·00183	0·00116
k_1 at 26°	0·00753	0·00618	0·00393	0·00225

TABLE XII.

Na-formate (g./litre).	Temp. coeff. k_{21}/k_{16} .	Temp. coeff. k_{26}/k_{21} .	Temp. coeff. k_{26}/k_{10} .
100	$\frac{0\cdot00366}{0\cdot00166} = 2\cdot2$	$\frac{0\cdot00753}{0\cdot00366} = 2\cdot05$	$\frac{0\cdot00753}{0\cdot00166} = 4\cdot5$
80	$\frac{0\cdot00290}{0\cdot00130} = 2\cdot2$	$\frac{0\cdot00618}{0\cdot00290} = 2\cdot1$	$\frac{0\cdot00618}{0\cdot00130} = 4\cdot7$
50	$\frac{0\cdot00183}{0\cdot000788} = 2\cdot3$	$\frac{0\cdot00393}{0\cdot00183} = 2\cdot1$	$\frac{0\cdot00393}{0\cdot000788} = 4\cdot9$
30	$\frac{0\cdot00116}{0\cdot000549} = 2\cdot1$	$\frac{0\cdot00225}{0\cdot00116} = 2\cdot07$	$\frac{0\cdot00225}{0\cdot000549} = 4\cdot1$

These results clearly show that the value of temperature coefficient increases as the velocity constant falls. Thus the dark temperature coefficient or the acceleration of the dark reaction depends on the initial velocity. If this is smaller, the acceleration is larger or the temperature coefficient is greater than when initial velocity is great. This is quite obvious, because the acceleration depends on the number of active molecules increased, and always the same fraction of inactive molecules is activated according to Maxwell's rule. Hence, when the velocity is small the number of inactive molecules is great and hence the acceleration due to temperature or temperature coefficient is great.

TABLE XIII.

Reaction with aqueous iodine.

$I_2 = 0.206$ g./litre. $HCOONa = 4$ g./litre. 50 c.c. of each solution mixed together and 10 c.c. of mixture titrated each time. Temp. = 16° .

Time.	Tbio.	k_1 .
0 min.	20.6 c.c.	—
30	12.8	0.00689
60	8.6	0.00634
90	4.95	0.00680
		mean 0.00667

TABLE XIV.

Velocity constant with the concentration of formate at 16° .

Na-formate (g./litre).	k_1 .	k_1 calc. on proportionality basis.
4.0	0.00667	0.00667
3.2	0.00536	0.00533
2.0	0.00323	0.00333
1.2	0.00212	0.00201

Thus the reaction is unimolecular with respect to both sodium formate and iodine.

Ghosh and Purkaystha (*loc. cit.*) have suggested from their experiments with bromine and organo-hydroxy acids that the order of the reaction with respect to halogen is bimolecular. Our results clearly have shown that at least in case of iodine, even in aqueous solution without the presence of KI, the order is unimolecular.

These observations therefore support the view of Bhagwat and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 191, 393) that the order of the reaction with respect to iodine is unimolecular in such cases.

The comparison of the results clearly shows that the velocity constant has tremendously increased in case of aqueous iodine for the same concentration of sodium formate. It is about 3000 times greater than the velocity when 44.6634 g. of KI per litre are present.

SUMMARY.

1. The dark reaction between sodium formate and iodine both in presence and absence of potassium iodide has been investigated and it is shown that order of the reaction with respect to iodine is always unity and never bimolecular as suggested by Ghosh and Purkaystha in case of bromine reaction.

2. The study of the effect of potassium chloride, potassium bromide, potassium iodide and potassium acetate shows that the reaction is accelerated by KCl and acceleration is proportional to the concentration of KCl. While KI retards the reaction KBr, has no effect on the reaction. It seems, therefore, that retarding effect of KI is due to the formation of KI_3 with I_2 thus diminishing the concentration of free iodine. It is found that when concentration of the sodium formate is high it is not necessary to add sodium acetate to get good velocity constants.

3. Measurements of temperature coefficient show that the value depends upon previous acceleration; greater the previous acceleration, smaller the temperature coefficient.

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